

TO SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC AND ANTI-CHOLESTEREMIC DRUGS BY RP- HPLC AND UV SPECTROSCOPY

¹*Mahajan Vivek R., ²Jalde Swapna R., ³Dr. Ingole R. D.

DJPS College of Pharmacy, Vill-Pohetakli, TQ-Patri, Dist-Parbhani, Maharashtra.

Article Received on 05 May 2026,
Article Revised on 25 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20470575>

*Corresponding Author

Mahajan Vivek R.

DJPS College of Pharmacy, Vill-
Pohetakli, TQ-Patri, Dist-Parbhani,
Maharashtra.

How to cite this Article: ¹*Mahajan Vivek R., ²Jalde Swapna R., ³Dr. Ingole R. D. (2026). To Simultaneous Estimation Of Anti-Diabetic And Anti Cholesteremic Drugs By Rp- Hplc And Uv Spectroscopy. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 1170–1179.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license

ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise, and economical analytical method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Glimpiride and Atorvastatin Calcium by RP-HPLC and UV spectroscopy in bulk and tablet dosage forms. Chromatographic separation in RP-HPLC was achieved using a C18 column with an optimized mobile phase under isocratic conditions. Both drugs showed well-resolved peaks with satisfactory retention times and system suitability parameters. The UV spectroscopic method was developed using simultaneous equation and absorbance correction methods at selected wavelengths. The developed methods were validated according to ICH guidelines. Validation parameters included linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. Excellent linearity was observed with correlation coefficients greater than 0.999 for both drugs. Recovery studies confirmed the accuracy of the

methods, while low %RSD values indicated good precision and reproducibility. The RP-HPLC method showed higher sensitivity and specificity compared to UV spectroscopy. The proposed methods were found suitable for routine quality control analysis of combined pharmaceutical formulations containing Glimpiride and Atorvastatin Calcium.

KEYWORDS: Glimpiride, Atorvastatin Calcium, RP-HPLC, UV Spectroscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Back ground: Glimpiride and Atorvastatin Calcium are commonly prescribed for the treatment of diabetes mellitus associated with hyperlipidemia. A validated RP-HPLC and UV spectroscopic method is essential for their simultaneous estimation in pharmaceutical

formulations for routine quality control analysis. Diabetes mellitus and hyperlipidemia are among the most common chronic metabolic disorders affecting millions of people worldwide. These conditions are often associated with severe complications such as cardiovascular diseases, kidney dysfunction, neuropathy, and stroke. In clinical practice, patients suffering from type 2 diabetes mellitus frequently exhibit abnormal lipid profiles, which necessitates the combined administration of anti-diabetic and lipid-lowering drugs. Glimepiride is a third-generation sulfonylurea widely used for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus by stimulating insulin secretion from pancreatic β -cells. Atorvastatin Calcium is a lipid-lowering agent belonging to the statin class, commonly prescribed to reduce cholesterol and triglyceride levels and to prevent cardiovascular complications. The simultaneous administration of these drugs has become increasingly common in combined therapy for diabetic patients with dyslipidemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1: list of chemicals.

S. No.	Chemicals and Solvents
1	Atorvastatin calcium and Glimepiride
2	Acetonitrile (HPLC Grade) Merck.
3	Milli-Q Water.
4	Potassium di-hydrogen orthophosphate (Analytical Grade) Rankem.
5	Sodium acetate (Analytical Grade) Rankem.

Table 2: List of Instruments.

S.No.	Instruments
1	UV spectrophotometer model SHIMADZU 1700 using quartz cell will be used. HPLC model LC-6600, CHEMITO Detector, with C18 column will be used and Dual λ absorbance UV detector.
2	C18 and C8 RP HPLC columns (250 X 4.6mm; 5.0 μ m)
3	Chromatographic system equipped with binary pumps, auto injector, oven And programmable UV detector.
4	Thermo Scientific Finn Pipette.
5	Millipore water system.
6	Metrohm pH meter
7	Denver weighing balance
8	Elma S 300H Ultra sonicator
9	10ml,50ml & 100 ml volumetric flasks
10	250 ml conical flask and Beakers

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Table 3: System suitability Parameter

Parameter	Atorvastatin Calcium	Glimepiride
Retention time	6.05	7.84
Purity angle	0.43	0.29
Purity threshold	0.93	1.03
Tailing factor	1.98	1,26
Theoretical plate	2986	3254

OBSERVATIONS: From the chromatogram, it was observed that there the resolution between peaks was more than 1.5. The theoretical plate count was more than 2000 and Tailing factor for peak was not more than 1.5.

Inference: The method passes System suitability

Figure 1: System suitability chromatogram.

Table 4: Validation Parameter.

Parameter	Atorvastatin Calcium	Glimepiride
Linearity range	50-150 μ g/ml	50-150 μ g/ml
Correlation co-efficient (R ²)	0.9899	0.9949
LOD	0.02 μ g/ml	0.01 μ g/ml
LOQ	0.05 μ g/ml	0.025 μ g/ml
%RSD for Recovery	% 0.39	%0.28

Fig. 2: Atorvastatin Calcium Validation.

Fig. 3: Glimepiride Validation.

9. CONCLUSION

The present study successfully developed and validated simple, precise, accurate, and economical RP-HPLC and UV spectroscopic methods for the simultaneous estimation of Glimepiride and Atorvastatin Calcium in combined dosage forms. Both methods complied with ICH validation guidelines and showed good accuracy, precision, linearity, and specificity. Among them, the RP-HPLC method demonstrated superior sensitivity and reliability for routine quality control analysis. Hence, the developed methods are suitable for regular pharmaceutical analysis and research applications.

REFERENCES

1. C Satinder ahuja, F.Stephen Scypinski. "Hand book of modern pharmaceutical analysis", 2nd Edn., (2003).
2. Beckett.A.H., and Stenlake.J.B, Practical pharmaceutical chemistry 4th edition part-1,2, Gary D.Christi, Analytical chemistry, 6th edition, 2004.
3. Gary D.Christian., Analytical chemistry, 6th edition, 2004.
4. Hemilton R.J and Swell, Introduction to HPLC, 2nd edition.
5. Douglas A.Skoog, Donal M.West,F.James Holler Stanley R.Crouch., Analytical chemistry, 8thedition.
6. H.H.Williard, L.L. Merit, F.A. Dean and F.A. Settle, Instrumental methods of analysis, 7th Edn, C.B.S. Publishers, New Delhi, 2002.
7. Balikak B. Shetty S.M, Scope and importance of analytical chemistry 5th edition.
8. David.Harvey, Modern Methods of Analytical Chemistry.
9. Kealey. D and Haines P.J,"Analytical chemistry", 1st edition.
10. ICH Topic Q2A, "Validation of Analytical Procedures": Text, 6th Nov 1996.
11. ICH Topic Q2B, "Validation of Analytical Procedures": Methodology, 6th Nov.

12. H.H. Willard, L.L. Merit, F.A. Dean and F.A. Settle, Instrumental methods of analysis, 7th edition, C. B.S Publishers, New Delhi.
13. Instrumental Methods of Analysis, 7th edition, C.B.S publishers, New Delhi.
14. Lloyd R. Snyder, Joseph J. Kirkland, Joseph L. Glajesh, Practical HPLC Method Development, 2nd Edition, 1997; 1-14.
15. Ewing G. W., Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis, McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ins., 2nd Ed., 1960; 3.
16. Lurie S. Ira and Wittwer, D. John Jr., HPLC in Forensic Chemistry, vii.
17. Jeffery G. H., Bassett J., Medham J. and Denney R. C., Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative.
18. Sethi PD.. "Quantitative Analysis of Drug in Pharmaceutical Formulation".
 - a. 2nd ed. CBS Publication 1993. [http://www.rxlist.com/Atorvastatin Calcium\) drug.html](http://www.rxlist.com/Atorvastatin%20Calcium%20drug.html) (the internet drug index). [http://www.rxlist.com/Glimepiride\) drug.html](http://www.rxlist.com/Glimepiride%20drug.html) (the internet drug index).
19. Brock G, Atorvastatin Calcium, Drugs Today, 2000; 36: 125-134.
20. Copper JDH, Muirhead DC, Taylor JE, Baker RP, J. chromatogr, B 1997; 701:87-95.
21. Pharmaceutical Forum (UCP), Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets monographs 1998; 24: 7182-7185.
22. Sacre P, Decononck E, DeBeer T, Courselle P, Vancauwenberghe R, Chiap P, Crommen J, DeeBeer j, "Comparison and combination of spectroscopic techniques for the detection of counterfeit medicine". J Pharm Biomed Ana., 2010; 53: 445-453.
23. Liu YM, Yang HC, Miao J.R. "Reversed-phase HPLC determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets. Yaowu. Fenxi. Zazhi., 2000; 20: 61-62.
24. Lee M, Min D, "Determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography and a case for the potential interaction of grape fruit juice with Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets". Ther. Drug Monit, 2001; 23(1): 21-26.
25. Kuchekar BS, Thakkar SV, Chothe PP, Hiremath MR, Shinde DB, "Spectrophotometric estimation of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in tablets". Ind J Pharma Sc., 2005; 1: 749-751.
26. Thangabalan B, Vadivel K, Sowjanya K, Tejaswi G, "Quantitative spectrophotometric determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in tablet formulation using urea as hydrotropic solubilizing agent". Res J Pharm Tech., 2011; 2(2): 235-239.

27. Reddy BPK, Reddy YR, "Validation and stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in pharmaceutical formulation and human plasma" *E-J Chem.*, 2008; 5: 1117-1122.
28. Draghmen N, Al-omari M, Badwan AA, Jaber AM, "Determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets and related substances in the commercial products and tablet dosage form using HPLC". *J Pharm Biomed Ana.*, 2001; 25: 483-492.
29. Reddy BP, Jaya prakash M, Sivaji K, Reddy SV, Reddy S V, "Validation and stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in pharmaceutical formulations". *Int J Applied Bio Pharm Tech.*, 2010; 1: 104-111.
30. Aboul-Enin HY, Hefnawy MM, "Rapid determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Glimepiride tablets in pharmaceutical preparation using monolithic silica HPMC column". *J Liq Chromato and Related Tech.*, 2003; 26(17): 2897-2908.
31. Pistos C, Papoutsis I, Dona A, Stefnidou M, Athanaselis S, Maravelias C, Spiliopeulou C, "Forensic Sc Int.", 2008; 178: 192-198
32. Shabbir N, Zaman M, Siddique W, Mudassir M, Alhuthali HM, Alzahrani AR, Rehman ZU, Imran M. Development and validation of an RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin calcium and ezetimibe. *Acta Chromatographica*, 2026 Feb 4; 1326-2025.
33. Bhatia NM, Patil R, More H, Chougale RD. Design of experiments based reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography method for estimation of metformin and glimepiride in combined dosage forms. *The Thai Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2026; 50(1): 4.
34. Bukke SP, Kusuma PK, Bhadrhu B, Shanmugam ST, Kumarachari RK, Narapureddy BR, Onohuean H. RP-HPLC method development, validation, and greenness profile evaluation: Concurrent quantification of telmisartan and atorvastatin calcium in combined pharmaceutical formulation. *Acta Chromatographica*, 2025; Aug 12.
35. Yadav M, Chauhan R, Singh R, Tiwari N. Development And Validation Of RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Quantification Of Three Anti-Diabetic Agents In Pharmaceutical Formulation. *Cuestiones de Fisioterapia*, 2025 Jan 10; 54(1): 715-20
36. Megha G, Kutty SV, Haribabu Y, Siddharth GJ, Anupama CP, Machado J, Divya V. Novel Validated Approach for the Simultaneous Determination of Lobeglitazone Sulfate and Glimepiride in its Pure and Combined Dosage Form Using Tandem Quantification Methods by UV-Vis Spectroscopy. *Journal of Applied Spectroscopy*, 2025 May; 92(2):

- 378-87.
37. Dhaigude RS, Dyade GK, Joshi HA, Purane LM, Lakade MM, Chandgude VS. Absorption Spectrophotometric Method Development for The Simultaneous Estimation of Anti-Diabetic Drugs Sitagliptin and Glimepiride. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis*, 2025 May 10; 15(2): 91-8.
 38. Hanooan WA, Abakaa AR, Azbar AS, Ali LI. Development of a spectroscopic approach for the estimation of glimepiride by oxidation reaction in an acidic environment and measurement of the area under the absorption curve using the UV-visible technique. *Babcock University Medical Journal*, 2025 Dec 31; 8(2): 463-71.
 39. Mali DP, Waghmare AV, Gaikwad DT. Simultaneous estimation of amlodipine and atorvastatin using UV-spectroscopy method. *Int. J. Pharm. Qual. Assu.* 2024;15:671-5.
 40. Patel D, Dobariya J, Pradhan P, Patel G, Meshram D. Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric methods for simultaneous estimation of Lobeglitazone Sulfate and Glimepiride in combined dosage form. *Drug Analytical Research*, 2024 Jul 19; 8(1): 62-9.
 41. Akabari AH, Mistry P, Patel SK, Surati J, Patel SP, Shah U. Simultaneous estimation of fimasartan potassium trihydrate and atorvastatin calcium with greenness assessment using HPLC and UV spectrophotometric methods. *Green Analytical Chemistry*, 2023 Sep 1;6: 100067.
 42. Ibesch S, Bitar Y, Trefi S. A New method for simultaneous qualitative and quantitative determination of amlodipine besylate and atorvastatin calcium in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations using transmission FT-IR spectroscopy. *Heliyon*, 2023 Mar 1; 9(3).
 43. Ahmad N, Bitar Y, Trefi S. Development and validation of a simple method for the determination of Atorvastatin calcium in pure and pharmaceutical formulations using spectrofluorimetry. *Heliyon*, 2023 Mar 1; 9(3).
 44. Marie AA, Hammad SF, Salim MM, Elkhodary MM, Kamal AH. Deduction of the operable design space of RP-HPLC technique for the simultaneous estimation of metformin, pioglitazone, and glimepiride. *Scientific reports*, 2023 Mar 16; 13(1): 4334.
 45. Chotaliya UJ, Dobariya HJ, Barad DL, Vyas AJ, Gol DA. Stability indicating RP-HPLC-DAD method for simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin calcium and teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate in synthetic mixture. *Analytical Chemistry Letters*, 2022 Sep 3; 12(5): 629-38
 46. Jayasundara UK, Herath HM, Kaushalya PV. Method development, validation, and concentration determination of metformin hydrochloride and atorvastatin calcium using

- UV-visible spectrophotometry. *J Anal Bioanal Tech.*, 2021; 12(2): 428.
47. Shaikh S. Simultaneous estimation of pioglitazone, glimepiride metformin hydrochloride in bulk tablet dosage form by UV, RP-HPLC method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis*. 2021.
 48. AHMAD S, NAWAJ SS. Development and Validation of Absorbance Subtraction Method for Simultaneous Determination of Atorvastatin Calcium and Sildenafil Using UV Spectrophotometer. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366)*. 2021 Jan 1; 13(1).
 49. Chafle D, Awale L. Development and validation of direct spectrophotometric method for the estimation of glimepiride. *Methodology*, 2021; Mar.
 50. Shaikh S. Simultaneous estimation of pioglitazone, glimepiride metformin hydrochloride in bulk tablet dosage form by UV, RP-HPLC method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis*, 2021.
 51. Sebaiy MM, El-Adl SM, Baraka MM, Hassan AA. Rapid RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of metformin, pioglitazone, and glimepiride in human plasma. *Acta Chromatographica*, 2020 Mar; 32(1): 16-21.
 52. Kumar A, Sharma AK, Dutt R. Reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography method development and validation for estimation of glimepiride in bulk and tablet dosage form. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance*, 2020 Jun 25; 11(02): 296-302.
 53. Pandey NK, Singh SK, Ghosh D, Khursheed R, Kumar R, Kapoor B, Kumar B, Awasthi A. Method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of glimepiride and simvastatin by using reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 2020; 13(4): 1655-9.
 54. Suneela, D.; Dhaneshwar, S.; Deshpande, P.; Patil, M. Development and validation of a method for simultaneous densitometric estimation of atorvastatin calcium and ezetimibe as the bulk drug and in tablet dosage forms. *Acta Chromatographica*, 2007; 19.
 55. Kumar, S. A.; Debnath, M.; Rao, J. V. L. N. S.; Sankar, D. G. New validated stability-indicating Rp-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin and ezetimibe in human plasma by using PDA detector. *Adv. Pharm. Bull*, 2015; 5: 385–91. <https://doi.org/10.15171/apb.2015.053>.
 56. Sirén, H. Atorvastatin and related compounds: review on analyses of pharmaceutical, blood and environmental samples, 2017.

57. Poli, A. Atorvastatin: pharmacological characteristics and lipid lowering effects. *Drugs*, 2007; 67(Suppl 1): 3–15. [https://doi.org/ 10.2165/00003495-200767001-00002](https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-200767001-00002).
58. Chohan, M. S.; Attimarad, M.; Venugopala, K. N.; Nair, A. B.; Sreeharsha, N.; Molina, E. I. P.; Kotnal, R. B.; Shafi, S.; David, M.; Shinu, P.; Altaysan, A. I.; Abdulmalek Ahmed Balgoname, A. A. Sensitivity enhanced ecofriendly UV spectrophotometric methods for quality control of telmisartan and benidipine formulations: comparison of whiteness and greenness with HPLC methods. *IJERPH.*, 2022; 19: 7260; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19127260>.
59. Patel, N.; Jayvadan, P. Analytical methodologies for determination of telmisartan: an overview. *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2013; 5: 17–22.
60. Gałuszka, A.; Migaszewski, Z. M.; Konieczka, P.; Namiesnik, J. Analytical eco-scale for assessing the greenness of analytical procedures. *Trac Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2012; 37: 61–72. [https://doi.org/ 10.1016/j.trac.2012.03.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2012.03.013).
61. Tobiszewski, M.; Namiesnik, J. Direct chromatographic methods in the context of green analytical chemistry. *Trac Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2012; 35, 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2012.02.006>
62. Magdy, M. A.; Farid, N. F.; Anwar, B. H.; Abdelhamid, N. S. Four greenness evaluations of two chromatographic methods: application to fluphenazine HCl and nortriptyline HCl pharmaceutical combination in presence of their potential impurities perphenazine and dibenzosuberone. *Chromatographia*, 2022; 85: 1075–86. [https:// doi.org/10.1007/s10337-022-04214-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10337-022-04214-3).
63. Jagirapu, B.; Harini, U.; Divya, M.; Sushma, P. Simultaneous estimation of telmisartan and atorvastatin calcium in API and tablet dosage form. *J. Drug Deliv. Ther.*, 2019; 9: 175–9. [https://doi.org/ 10.22270/jddt.v9i1.2268](https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v9i1.2268).
64. Gv, S. K.; Rajendraprasad, Y.; Chandrashekar, S. Development and validation of reversed-phase HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin calcium and telmisartan in tablet dosage form. *Int. J. PharmTech Res.*, 2010; 2: 463–70.
65. Alhazmi, H. A.; Alnami, A. M.; Arishi, M. A. A.; Alameer, R. K.; Al Bratty, M.; Rehman, Z. U.; Javed, S. A.; Arbab, I. A. A fast and validated reversed-phase HPLC method for simultaneous determination of simvastatin, atorvastatin, telmisartan and irbesartan in bulk drugs and tablet formulations. *Sci. Pharm.*, 2017; 86(1):<https://doi.org/10.3390/scipharm86010001>.